

Designing materials experiences through passing of time – Material driven design method applied to mycelium-based composites

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Abstract As part of a research about the relationship between time and design through the topic of materials and processes, this paper presents experimentation on a novel material. New materials are emerging through a Do-It-Yourself approach encouraged by Open source behaviors and trans-disciplinary design. These materials become representative of new values, aesthetics and dynamics, which lead to an emotional bonding with the user and the designer. The need of applying a method suitable for the design of these materials is emerging. New tools for selecting, exploring and designing materials based on experience, senses and emotion are starting to be available and applied. Mycelium-based DIY material have a strong potential and might be a perfect candidate to experiment with an experience-based method, that is the Material Driven Design method. Through this method a material experience related to the passing of time and consistent with the material qualities and characteristics was developed. Combining a novel material with a novel method might lead to development both on the material and on the method itself.

Keywords *Material-driven design, Passing of time, Mycelium-based composites, Materials experience, Trans-disciplinary design*

Introduction

The study presented here shows an experimentation process on a mycelium-based composite, through *Material Driven Design* (MDD) method, that is a method supporting designers in understanding and designing the experience that the user have with and through a certain material (Karana et. al, 2015). The aim of this study was to test the method in designing a materials experience consistent with the qualities of the material itself. The inner and peculiar features of this mycelium-based composite characterized by its spontaneity and dynamism led to develop a poetic material experience linked to passing of time, which is expressed by the emotional bonding through memories, the spontaneous growing process of the living material, the signs and traces of time and usage and the imperfect aesthetic given by its rudimentary and low tech process.

The paper describes the study through the following contents: (1) Starting with a description of the **state of the art**, an exploration of the changing context of design of materials which is characterized by emerging practices and theories around Do-It-Yourself (DIY) is performed. Open Source, trans-disciplinarity and the established approach based on emotions, senses and experience, more than on technical and functional issues are addressed as well. (2) A **mycelium-based composite** is described focusing on its potential properties and its manufacturing process. (3) The main steps of the MDD **method** are applied to

the composite in order to: understanding the material, creating the material experience vision, manifesting the material experience pattern and designing the material concept. (4) The tangible and intangible **results** are then presented in the form of findings, insights, visions and material samples. (5) In the **discussion and conclusions** a critical view is presented along with the challenges that could be undertaken, the relevance of the method tested and guidelines about the further steps.

State of the art

An overview of the design context from which our study arises is addressed. As a precondition, it is needed to state that more and more designers are showing interest in materials and deepening or discovering their role as designers of materials themselves, moving away from a product-centered approach. They operate on processes, surface treatments or on the formulation itself in order to produce material innovation. It is evident that materials enormously influence the products as a whole, because they constitute their physicality and substance.

On a par with product design, theories and practices about design of materials are changing (Karana et al., 2016). This dynamic context is characterized by several intertwined factors: the established interest in the intangible characteristics of design – sensoriality, meaning, experience, among others – which led to the

development of new tools and methods for materials selection, exploration and design (Pedgley, 2014; Akın & Pedgley, 2016); the emergence of a new aesthetic related to imperfection and aging (Rognoli & Karana, 2014; Saito, 2010); the growth of transdisciplinarity in design (Brown, 2009; Aldersey et. al, 2008); the diffusion of new way to look and develop materials from a design point of view that brought to the tuning of a new class of materials, as Do-It-Yourself Materials (DIY-M) (Rognoli et al., 2015).

In fact, as described in detail by scholars (Rognoli et. al, 2015) the democratization of technological practices is bringing to an easier accessibility to technologies both owned, through cheap and flexible tools, and shared, through the notion of open source. The concept and practices of open source are manifesting in the context of materials for design through databases, physical and digital material libraries, tools for selection and inspiration, digital platforms like forums where the users, both professionals and non-professionals, are able to find information on materials and manufacturing process, even update, add materials, information and opinions, and ultimately share their experience. Producers also support open source by publishing on the Internet the recipes of their materials, like the growing materials by Ecovative Design ("Ecovative's Myco Make instructions", n.d.) and by Suzanne Lee (Lee, n.d.). Open source it is becoming more evident through Fablabs, factories and workshops for prototyping and experimentation. For sure, the diffusion of open source philosophy gets stronger the possibility for the designers to access to data related to different fields and disciplines, meet professionals with different background and start collaborations. Thus a trans-disciplinary approach in design becomes more and more diffused. From natural sciences, through design, culinary arts arriving into medicine, it is visible to our eyes how the most distant fields are starting to encounter synergy to work together. This is the case of DIYBio Labs ("DIYbio Labs homepage", 2008) where designers and scientists, namely DIY biologist, can meet and collaborate on shared project. Through cross-pollination of knowledge, practices, methods, technologies, formal languages and inspirations designers are discovering alternatives to conventions both technically and aesthetically to propose new solutions that are innovative, original, competitive, affordable and sustainable that can overtake conventional solutions provided by industries and mass production (Aldersey-Williams et al., 2008).

The growth of trans-disciplinary collaborations, combined with the democratization of technologies (Tannenbaum et al, 2013) and the diffusion of fablabs, are empowering designers to gain independence from industries. Designers are being able to self-produce materials, tools and artifacts. They can satisfy their needs of autonomy, personalization and appropriation to better express their design idea, contributing to create a different emotional relationship between artifacts and users. Materials that are self-produced by designers can be called Do-It-Yourself materials (DIY-M) (Rognoli et al., 2015). DIY Materials elicit new aesthetics and new dynamics. Usually they are

produced with local resources, promoting sustainability, reducing the costs and bringing out an emotional bonding through memories. They are characterized by the aesthetic of imperfection, which makes the material more human and emotionally connected to the user. Because they are self-made, the designer establish a personal connection with his or her creations. Through a "hands-on" approach (Nimkulrat, 2012) the designer is learning by doing and collecting experience and a know-how about that material; the user perceives the value of something self-made like it happens for handcraft. They are shared and open source allowing perpetual updates, improvements and developments made by others, generating also variations. According to Kuznetsov & Paulos (2010), any modification or repair action without the aid of paid professionals is considered a DIY practice. Moreover these practices are usually led by experimental, and sometimes artistic, impulses. Therefore, in order to produce applicable, acceptable and durable results they need to be guided by a structured design method. They are also experimental and uncompleted proposals, so their properties, limits and possibilities should be observed and understood through a method, in order to make further developments. In addition, a method is needed because another crucial point is that these materials are new, unknown and without an identity. One can state that "people can't recognize and understand the materials, because they don't have previous experience with them".

This novel class of materials transversely embraces a new design aesthetic characterized by imperfection and the passing of time (Rognoli & Karana, 2014). Designers are showing more and more interests in the effect of time and usage on artifacts, materials and processes (Annicchiaricco & Van Der Rossem, 2012). They are considering the values and experiences given by inevitable and natural aging and, as modern alchemist, they are experimenting with ingredients and solutions in order to accelerate aging and enhance the marks of time and use (Ostuzzi et al., 2011).

New tools and methods for material selection are being developed by scholars in the last 15 years (Pedgley, 2014). More than technical properties they are based on sensorial appreciation, meanings, emotion, experience and identity. In a few words, what Karana and colleagues called before *Intangible characteristic of materials* or ICM (Karana et al., 2007; Karana et al., 2010) and now call *intangible sparks* (Karana et al., 2015 a). In addition to these tools a novel method for material exploration and design focusing on Material experience and combining practical experimentation, user studies and meta-design vision was recently introduced, namely the Material-Driven Design method (MDD) (Karana et al., 2015 b). Connected to the idea of Product Experience (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) the concept of Material experience by Karana is a key factor: "Material experience is the experience that people have through and with materials" (Karana, 2009), considering senses, meanings, emotions (Karana, 2009) and performing (Giaccardi and Karana, 2015). The user involvement and a hands-on approach required in the MDD appear

to be crucial in the understanding and experimentation with new materials in order to make them meaningful.

Taking into account this changing context, it was decided to focus on Mycelium based composite as a material that represent the best candidate to experiment with in order to understand it and develop a meaningful experience connected to passing of time and based on its characteristics and qualities. Mycelium based composite is characterized by an open source and DIY approach, together with an aesthetic process related to trans-disciplinarity, to passing of time and imperfection. The use of this natural material in everyday life was firstly promoted by the american mycologist Paul Stamets in his book *Mycelium Running: how mycelium can save the world?* (2005) and supported by a huge community as we can note from websites and dedicated pages on diy ("DIY page: Make a mycelium starter", n.d), Ukfungusday ("Ukfungusday homepage", n.d.), fungi expert David Moore website (2011), and others.

The relevance of this material is revealed by the interests shown by design education and research which are running research projects and didactic activities focused on it.

Mycelium-based composite

The aim of the research and the design context described so far was focused on this specific material. Herewith is presented the description of this DIY bio-composite material based on mycelium – *namely the roots of fungus* – and natural substrate derived from agricultural waste. It is characterized by a low tech and slow process, which is respectful of natural rhythm of growing. As a matter of fact, the process is actually the growing of mycelium through and over the fibers of the natural substrate, inside a mould, in several days (depending on the environment). After baking, the material is stabilized and inert since the mycelium is dried and dead. As a result, a compact, lightweight and insulating material arise. The main feature addressed is sustainability: entirely natural, derived from byproducts, compostable and Cradle To Cradle (Braungart & Mc. Donough, 2002).

Although the material and the process have been present in nature, during the last seven years it has been adopted and developed as design and construction material by the American company Ecovative Design ("Ecovative Design's homepage", n.d.). Other companies and designers from all over the world are showing interest in the material and are studying it and experimenting on it according to open source and DIY logics. Currently is commercially applied in packaging, furniture and insulation for architecture, whereas the experimental practices are focusing on small objects and accessories like vases, lamps, shoes, mat, ecc. One interesting application from Ecovative Design is as surf-boards and buoys.

The use of this substance as a material is novel, relatively unknown and its identity is not already defined and solid. Companies and designer that provide it or support it didn't develop a ultimate

version of it and have not already a deep understanding and knowledge of its properties, limits, constraints, and potentiality.

In general it seems a material with a high potential and suitable to be studied, to experiment with, and to develop further applying a method. Being open source, DIY and low-tech, it allows to examine easily and directly the process and to interact with it.

The process began from the Grow-It-Yourself (or Myco Make) kits sold by Ecovative Design (Ecovative Design's GIY kit, n.d.). They consist in plastic bag inside which mycelium is already inserted through the natural substrate, then dehydrated, and ready to be re-hydrated with flour and water. This choice is motivated by the necessity of restricting time and failure risks and to being supported by the assistance provided by the company.

Method

Starting from this formulation the MDD method (Karana, et al, 2015) was followed in order to understand the material and its process and to define a new vision from which design a meaningful material experience and define new development directions. The research presented was developed in several steps according to the method.

Step 1. Understanding the material

The first step of the process is related to the study of the material and is made of three simultaneous activities: tinkering with the material; user studies; material benchmark studies.

Step 1.1. Tinkering with the material

Through this step characterized by a hands-on approach it is possible to obtain information about the material's properties and how it can be processed and shaped. Furthermore the designer can have an experience of the material in first person. This step is crucial when technical data sheets are not available or are not completed, e.g. for experimental or semi-developed materials. We tested the material through (1) tinkering of the material during the process and (2) tinkering of the material after the process.

The first practice aims to deeply understand the manufacturing process of the material and comprehend the relationship between the variables of the process and certain technical and expressive-sensorial features of the processed material. Throughout four months, the process was performed six times with a pace of 2-3 weeks, producing more than 130 samples with different qualities starting from 15 kits. Each time several changes were introduced during the process as follows: including other materials; adding new ingredients; using molds of different shapes and sizes; applying textures and colors; changing the room temperature while growing; varying the duration of the process; reducing the length of the natural fibers; controlling the temperature and duration of baking. To all these variables, the unrestrained ones such as the environmental, must be considered as they often led to unexpected results: moisture; temperature and

Figure 1-6. Activities and tests of the tinkering with the material phase.

weather condition of the location in which the material grows – including diverse geographical areas – could affect the results.

The second practice aims to understand the possible surface treatments as well as to identify the resistance of the material. Different interventions were performed on the processed samples: dyeing, texturization, tests for fire resistance, water resistance, uv resistance, weather resistance, scratch resistance, tensile strength, ecc.

Material tinkering revealed to be a perpetual activity from the beginning to the end of the process, i.e. from the first attempts to the final samples.

Step 1.2. User studies

At this stage the material was introduced to groups of people, that could be addressed as possible users of it or of any artifact produced with the material – or perhaps the self-producers of the material. This step aims to describe the experiential characterization of the material.

The information was obtained through three different activities:

1. Individual interviews took place between September and November 2015.
2. Structured workshop with different activities (questionnaires, group interviews and discussions, creative activities and brainstorming sessions) with 34 students from the first year of Product Design for Innovation Master Course at Politecnico di Milano on 14th and 16th October, 2015.
3. Structured workshop with different activities (questionnaires, creative activities, practical workshop of material production, informative and educational activities) with unselected users during the third anniversary of *Coltivando*, the

convivial urban farming garden at Politecnico di Milano, on 17th October, 2015.

The questionnaire was developed in the form of a 8 pages booklet structured as a “sensorial journey” or “sensorial exploration”. To each user or group of users a sample of material was given to examine with a sequential method: sight, touch, smell, the perception of taste through smell and sound. Through this gradual exploration the user was asked to isolate each sense from the others. During sight examination a request to describe the expectation of tactile, smell, taste and sound characteristics was made in order to highlight accordance and discordance through sight expectations and real perceptions, since it was a relatively unknown material. Three more sections were added: technical properties, lifecycle, conclusion.

In order to obtain quantitative information, the Meaning Driven Material Selection (MDMS) Tool (Karana, 2009) was chosen to answer different sensorial scale ratings. With such tool, the user is able to indicate how the material is perceived in a range of seven values between two different characteristics, (e.g. soft and hard). Following Mariet Sauerwein (Sauerwein, 2015) a contribution to the tool was inserted by adding sound, smell and taste characteristic charts, senses relevance and pleasantness chart and properties charts. It is important to underline that for such selection of the characteristics to add in the charts, the main reference was the Expressive-Sensorial Atlas (Rognoli, 2004; Rognoli, 2010).

Qualitative data was collected by adding open questions in each section of the questionnaire. During the so called “sensorial journey” it was possible to investigate about the material experience throughout the four experiential levels: sensorial, emotional, interpretative, performative. For each sense the user

Figure 7-12. Images from the workshops.

was asked around sensorial perception. Activities around meanings, opinions, reactions and behaviors completed the step.

Step 1.3. Benchmark studies

A comparative analysis between the material and other materials that might be alternatives of it was performed, in order to highlight differences and similarities, weaknesses, strong points and opportunities. For the comparison three categories of materials were selected: (1) mycelium-based materials produced by companies, on the market or on development with announced commercialization; (2) concepts and experimentations of mycelium-based material made by designers and students; (3) other produced materials that have some similarities with the material and can be substitutes of it. As a tool, we used tables in which we compare the materials by their characteristics, properties, applications and values.

Step 2. Creating the material experience vision

This step aims to support the designer in summarizing the results of the previous one by putting them in relations in a coherent whole in order to bring about relevant and critical issues and to define a unique and meaningful vision. As suggested in *MDD* method, some techniques from Vision in Design *ViP* method (Hekkert & van Dijk 2011) were considered: sequentially, clusterization of data, organization of a perceptual map naming axes with opposite values and defining four direction areas. Contrasting the method, the competitors identified in the benchmarking were mapped as well according to their vision and values. That helps to understand strategic blank spaces, i.e. opportunity areas, and consequently to define a vision statement.

Step 3. Manifesting the material experience pattern

At this stage the pattern of formal qualities was defined, like the technical and expressive-sensorial characteristics to emphasize or even transfer to the material in order to make it consistent with the vision. To achieve that goal, two meanings consistent with the vision through a semantic research utilizing mind maps as a support tool were identified.

Once the meanings were defined the necessity to identify the pattern of formal qualities linked to the meanings and through them to the vision became the next step. As suggested in *MDD* we involved the user once again through *MDMS* Tool to assure an authentic pattern.

Having the opportunity sometimes to interact directly with interviewed people in their home environment it was possible to ask them to show us physical objects instead of pictures allowing us to observe the interactions between people and the selected objects in terms of emotions and performances.

The interviews were asked for both meanings. The results were organized and visualized through the modality described in the *MDMS* Tool, i.e. a chart of values and a collection of images. To visualize and to organize the information we used also another tool by Elvin Karana, the Meanings of Materials (*MoM*) Tool. In this way we could summarize the information into different categories and subcategories, i.e. meanings, users (age, gender, nationality, fields), materials (technical properties and sensorial properties), product (manufacturing process, finishes, function, shape). We also add to the framework the category interaction (performative interaction, emotional interaction). In the sub-category sensorial properties we added a colour palette, since colour revealed to be a key factor in the perception of the material and to

have a strong connection with the meaning. We added finishes (surface treatments) as a subcategory of product.

Step 4. Designing the material concept

At this stage the identified pattern was applied to the material in order to make it consistent with the vision. To do that the experience obtained from the tinkering was considered as well. Thanks to the experience obtained from tinkering, a set of samples as concepts of further developed material were produced.

Results

Several amount of findings emerged through all the method, in particular from the first step, e.g. “understanding the material”. We obtained hundreds of data on the material properties, process and perception. Through the production of more than 130 samples and the application of different treatments on them, key issues like the material properties and final appearance vary with time. Those changes are conditioned depending on the time of the process, to the environment where the process takes place (temperature, moisture, aeration), the moulding techniques (pressure, mould’s size, breathability), the the components (fibers length, fibers colour), and the interaction with other materials. Different ways of interacting with the material and different climate and geographical conditions can lead to very different results. Because mycelium is a living and spontaneous material is difficult to completely control the process even in a laboratory or with an industrial or computerized process. Imperfection and irregularity are the main features of the material. The components confer a fibrous, amorphous, irregular and uneven appearance. Areas with different degrees of softness and roughness coexist in a small portion of surface according to the distribution of mycelium and fibers. Furthermore on the material the marks of the manufacturing process become always visible: moulding parting lines, flashing and burn marks. Through user studies it was possible to understand that people generally didn’t know the material but recognized it as made by two different components. They easily recognized the “brown part” as “natural fibers, sawdust, wood chips, dried plants, branches, hay or hemp” while the “white part” was not recognized as fungus and was pointed as made of natural or synthetic foam. Thus is not completely recognizable as biodegradable, compostable, and made from by-products, and consequently the grade of sustainability by being natural. Nevertheless they addressed as “natural” and “ecological”, and as “simple”, “modest”, “affordable”, “hand-craft” and “imperfect”. From their explanations it is due to its imperfect, fibrous and inaccurate aesthetic. The analogy with a rustic and country context is diffused because of its appearance and smell which reminds hay. Through this association the material recalls positive and nostalgic feelings that link the user to modest, genuine and childhood reality. Some of the interviews linked it to traditional or old materials diffused in their material culture. A peculiar analogy with food was identified because of its colors, roughness, irregularity and burning process that make it similar to “white chocolate, homemade bread and cheese”.

Figure 13. The structure where the material samples were placed to grow.

From the benchmark studies became clear that the companies that produce and sell the material – i.e. Ecovative Design and Mycoworks – underline the value of sustainability and of performances. They often try to hide its natural appearance making it most similar as possible to other materials and using lamination, giving it the idea of sustainable surrogate of polystyrene, cork, wood, ecc. It is visible that in a controlled environment and with an industrial process the material appears more homogeneous and performing. On the contrary, concept and experimentation from designers and students working with a DIY process, materials appear similar to the samples we produced showing the same levels of imperfection and irregularity. They push the vision to other values like the poetry of the process - e.g. *Officina Corpuscoli*, attempts of luxury identity - e.g. *Mycelial forms* (Hein, n.d), the therapeutic properties of fungus - e.g. *Vivorium* (Schachtschneider, n.d.), the spontaneity of the material - e.g. *Myx*. Comparing the material with other substitutes (i.e. expanded polystyrene, expanded polyethylene, chipboard, cork, natural beton, plasterboard, edimare, pumice), it is characterized by irregularity, unprocessed appearance, sustainability and the natural and slow process.

With the techniques and tools described in the method, all this data led to a vision statement based on an emotional bonding caused by memories between user and the material: “I want that the user is involved in an authentic bonding with the material because it is recognized as matter of time and of memories, filled with history and experience, like an artifact modeled by an artisan and subject to the marks of time”.

Through the meanings “genuine” and “spontaneous”, using the tools and the techniques described in the process, a material experience pattern was defined: irregular and fibrous texture; matt, opaque and not reflective surfaces; neutral and earthy colors through natural dyeing; marks of the process and of time, inclusions of other natural materials; possibility to process the material modeling it manually, without molds; rounded, enveloping and rounded shapes.

Figure 14-15. The final samples.

Figure 16. Textures applications.

Figure 17-18. Seeds inclusions give an expressive characterization to the samples.

Figure 19-20. Seeds released gel that allows to shape the material like clay.

Figure 21-22. Linum seeds germinate enhancing the "spontaneous" meaning.

Using the pattern as inspirational hints and design guidelines, a set of final samples consistent with the vision were developed operating through rough textures, natural dyeing, inclusion of natural and irregular materials. In particular the inclusion of psyllium, chia and linum seeds brought a functional and expressive contribution. These seeds release a gel that allows to shape the material without the use of moulds, similarly to clay and make it more resistant. The tactual and visual richness of the material is increased: without the use of a mould mycelium is able to grow more making the material more velvety and softer; seeds create a genuine visual pattern on the surface. Surprisingly linum seeds germinate during the process, reinforcing the "spontaneous" meaning.

Discussion

At this stage it is clear that the material is interesting because of its unique qualities, properties, possible applications and sustainable features. In addition the method applied allowed us to develop a unique and original vision in order to elicit a meaningful material experience for the user, valorizing the concept of passing of time. The first three steps of the method were fully applied while the last one was addressed

partially, without the development of a product concept. It became clear thus, that the first three steps are well described and structured and can be performed producing excellent outcomes which fully met our goals and expectations, whereas the last one requires a more solid structure in terms of guidelines and activities.

Following MDD method the next step should be the identification of meaningful and innovative areas of application consistent with the vision. Some ideas of application and concepts have already emerged from the first step (creative activities about applications) and in the third steps (product category). We had a set of information about application in forms of sketches and descriptions (step 1), images and processed data (step 3). Anyway we suggest that a workshop activity could be organized where the participants are given the final samples and are asked to describe, sketch or design some concept ideas consistent to the meanings or to the vision. They might be helped also giving them the data and images coming from the third step. After that we should select the most promising concept and develop some prototypes.

Different challenges and critical issues are in front of

us if we want to make further development. The first challenge is about the validation of the success of the samples development according to the vision. It is necessary to understand whether the users perceive the new material identity, whether their material experience has changed, whether the features on which we focused are strengthened. This may be validated through further user-studies in the form of workshops, interviews, questionnaires and surveys. All these new data should be compared with the data from the previous user studies.

The second one is related to the acceptance of the material by the market. It may seem not suitable for the large-market logics as a consumer good because of its aesthetic, imperfection, imprecision, fragility, instability, variability. This is why we imagine it produced in a semi-handcrafting dimension.

Another challenge is validating the applications that involve contact with the human body, contact with food and kitchen contextualization both from a psychological and biological perspective: mycophobia is a diffused psychological condition, as well mushroom allergy; the possibility of substances transfer from mycelium and other organic bodies should be tested. Developing prototypes, placing them in a context and conducting further user-studies might clarify the psychological issues, whereas biological tests might answer to the biological ones.

Speaking about the tools and the method, we started from a method on progress and we adapt it to our necessity. We also added tools, modified some others, for instance in the MoM tool by introducing new categories and subcategories, and we deepen some steps like the user studies.

Now that we learnt how to do it, next step is starting from the basis of the material choosing the ingredients from local resources and not the diy kit from a company.

Conclusions

The study presented here shows an experimentation process on a mycelium-based composite. The goal set at the beginning of the study was firmly achieved. Namely, understanding the material and developing an experience that enhance its qualities and characteristics related to the passing of time, adding value to the material, making it meaningful and opening new development directions. Eventually the results revealed to be consistent with the expectations. Furthermore, tinkering with a novel material brought to unexpected and inspiring results. As a result of the process, a novel and meaningful use of mycelium-based composites were identified, by emphasizing its spontaneous, imperfect and uncontrollable characteristics and by avoiding to strive for the adoption of a standard and industrial identity.

As presented, the improvement around the sensibility to understand the materials was evident focusing particularly on sensorial qualities. This was possible thanks to direct tinkering on materials. Indeed a "hands-on" approach proved to be crucial and

inextricable in the understanding of the material and of *what the material does* (Karana et. al., 2015 b).

It was an iterative journey of trial and error in which we learnt from both successes and failure. Through this practice experience and familiarity in dealing with the material and a *know-how* of the process was acquired. This know-how is even valuable considering that the material is novel, experimental and has promising properties, applications and sustainable features.

Another crucial issue was the user integration at different stage of the design process, from the understanding of the material to the concepts development. Through this kind of collaborative design it was possible to apply and improve some user-studies techniques and to build them up with a material-based approach.

Furthermore the learning of methods and tools by their application was a key point of the process and for our own training and improvement.

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Appendix 1. User studies - Questionnaire

Appendix 2. User studies - data charts

Appendix 3. User studies - Persona tool

ALESSANDRO
IL DIFFIDENTE
27 ANNI
GRAFICO

<<Questo materiale alla vista mi perprime. Non mi piace perché è molto irregolare, sembra rovinato. Sembra una buccia d'arancia. Mi disgusta perché sembra anche un formaggio. Concettualmente mi dà un'idea di sporcizia e di disordine, anche se naturale in un certo senso. Anche se non sono sicuro che sia completamente naturale. Sembra fatto di gesso, oppure stucco, oppure con una schiuma sintetica. Sembra artificiale, ma che vuole imitare il naturale. Non apprezco la sua superficie perché non di qualità. Insomma, si capisce che è meno raffinato di altri materiali, che non è di qualità, che è poco durevole. Io in casa mia non lo vorrei mai. Anche perché sembra molto fragile: sembra che si graffi e si rovini solamente a guardarlo. Secondo me per poter essere utilizzato deve essere ricoperto da altri materiali. Non deve essere mostrato. Oppure deve essere utilizzato come materiale secondario o usa e getta. Anche perché a vederlo non sembra avere particolari capacità meccaniche, né a trazione, né a compressione. Ma proviamo a toccarlo: beh, le mie idee sono confermate. Anche se è più resistente di come me lo immaginavo sono ancora molto critico. Non lo trovo piacevole a causa della sua irregolarità e fragilità superficiale. All'olfatto l'odore è acido e disgustoso: sento una nota principale di cantina umida, cassette di legno, stalla>>

SERENA
L'ENTUSIASTA
42 ANNI
EDUCATRICE

<<Appena ho visto il materiale mia ha dato un'idea di calore, accoglienza e calma: mi rimanda ad ambienti incontaminati e rurali, a una campagna senza la tecnologia. Questa cosa mi tranquillizza e mi dà un senso di calma. E si vede che tutela l'ambiente perché chiaramente è naturale, anche se non capisco di cosa è fatto. Sono sicura di potermi fidare. Questa idea di bucolico mi rimanda a un significato romantico del materiale. Ah, un'altra cosa è che mi ricorda qualcosa da mangiare, un torrone, una meringa o del cioccolato bianco. Già alla vista mi ispira molte emozioni positive e sono molto curiosa di toccarlo. Al tatto la mano scivola in modo piacevole sulla superficie. Ha un lato molto soffice. È un'emozione calma di gioco, relax perché leggero e morbido. Dici che la morbidezza è la sua qualità caratterizzante. Al tatto mi dà un'idea di riposo, rilassatezza, protezione, sicurezza e familiarità. Sembra a tratti anche una pagnotta: mi dà un'idea di casa, infanzia, dolcezza. Mi piace perché è morbido e leggero, non pericoloso, mi rimanda al gioco e all'infanzia: vorrei sdraiarmi sopra, come su un materassino per lo yoga, o camminarci sopra, per sentire i piedi che affondano. È bello perché ha delle parti lisce e altre ruvide: divertenti! All'olfatto è veramente buono: me lo mangerei! All'aspetto mi piace perché mi fa sentire protetto. Mi piacerebbe molto usarlo>>

EMILIO
L'INTERESSATO
34 ANNI
ARTISTA

<<Che materiale interessante e inusuale! Direi che è un composto naturale e sostenibile di quelli che realizzano ora, come quello a base di canapa. La sua identità naturale non è celata: i materiali che lo compongono gli danno un aspetto graziosamente umile. È molto onesto in questo: fa vedere i materiali che lo compongono. Credo che l'aspetto costituisca la sua stessa estetica: economico, leggero e immediato. Al tatto è molto ricco. Ricorda qualcosa di roccioso, o qualcosa di molto antico, per la sua ruvidità. Ma non è solo ruvido. È anche morbido. Che aspetto interessante! Non sembra avere proprietà tecniche innovative, ma nelle sue semplicità è interessante. Mi sembra semplice ma rielaborato in modo innovativo senza però diventare o voler sembrare ultra tecnologico. Ricorda un ritorno "primitivo" ai materiali semplici che non necessitano di ricerche esorbitanti sulla reperibilità. È evidente la sua natura sperimentale, ed è bello che ci si stia muovendo in questa direzione. È un materiale che vedrei bene nel futuro che vorrei io. Richiama anche il mondo dell'artigianato e del DIY. Racconta, nella sua umiltà e nel suo essere democratico, una storia legata all'artigianato. Il tempo del processo, secondo me, giustifica il costo. Ma questo materiale non sa raccontarsi completamente. Si può intervenire: la geo-caratterizzazione può essere molto rilevante>>

ROBERTA
LA CONFUSA
23 ANNI
STUDENTESSA

<<È un materiale strano. Alla vista mi incuriosisce, ma allo stesso tempo mi disgusta. Credo che sia relativamente pesante, molto duro e rigido, molto ruvido. La sua immagine mi ispira dei sentimenti un po' piacevoli: credo che anche all'odore non sia piacevole. Ma nel momento in cui lo tocco il materiale mi sorprende molto. Alla vista pensavo che fosse molto pesante e corposo. Al contrario è leggerissimo e mi trasmette piacere. Da una sensazione di vuoto interno. Inoltre mi aspettavo non fosse per niente flessibile. Mi ha sorpreso per la sua flessibilità. Alla vista sembrava più fragile e poroso. Invece ora mi colpisce per la sua compattezza e solidità. La superficie è piana e più liscia e morbida di come immaginavo. Anzi la immaginavo proprio al contrario. Invece è molto bello perché liscio e leggero. Alla vista sembra più friabile di come è. Pensavo che avesse un odore intenso e sgradevole probabilmente come l'uovo. Invece sa di menta e sigarette. Nonostante mi abbia colpito, non sono sicura che mi piaccia, e credo che ci siano ancora molte cose da sviluppare. È evidente la sua natura sperimentale. Deve essere migliorato, ma è interessante e ambizioso. Non è un materiale che apprezco come materiale da usare, è interessante solo da studiare>>

Appendix 4. Benchmark studies - Comparative charts

CHARACTERISTICS	irregularity	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	fibrosity	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	roughness	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	softness	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	insulation	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	resistance	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	weight	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	flexibility	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	building	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	packaging	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
APPLICATIONS	water related	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	furniture	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	product	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	body-related	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	values	//	surrugate sustainability versatility / DIY education	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability

Appendix 7. Pattern - semantic map

Appendix 8. Pattern - MDMS tool

Appendix 9. Pattern - MoM tool

